

EPIC-WE LEGACIES

Games through Culture EXPO Catalogue

EPIC-WE Games EXPO @ ARoS
February 3, 2026 - Aarhus, Denmark

EPIC-WE
Empowered Participants through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

Funded by
the European Union

EPIC-WE LEGACIES

Games through Culture

EXPO Catalogue

EPIC-WE Legacies: Games through Culture EXPO Catalogue

© EPIC-WE Project, 2026

Grant Agreement ID: 101095058

Project DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15349595

Copyright:

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License

This publication can be viewed online and downloaded as pdf.

Please visit www.epic-we.eu

Collected & Edited by:

Rikke Toft Nørgård

Kasper M. Nørmark

Ditte Brunø Søndergaard

Regitze Mai Møller

Sisse Siig Kristensen

Sabrina Louise Albin Andersen

Design by:

Sisse Siig Kristensen

Sabrina Louise Albin Andersen

We would like to extend our sincere thanks to all EPIC-WE partners and all the young EPIC-WE game jammers who have contributed with epic games, visuals, texts, and other materials. Without them there would be no epic we, no epic legacy, and no EXPO catalogue.

How to cite:

Nørgård, R. T., Nørmark, K. M., Søndergaard, D. B., Møller, R. M., Kristensen, S. S. & Andersen, S. L. A. (2026). *EPIC-WE Legacies: Games through Culture EXPO Catalogue*.

Zenodo. [↓](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18461443)

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18461443

Funded by
the European Union

EPIC-WE

Empowered Participation through Ideating
Cultural Worlds and Environments

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

TABLE OF CONTENT

Introduction

- 1 Games Through Culture
- 2 Foreword ARoS

Featured Cultural Games

- 3 Introduction Games Aarhus
- 5 Metamorphosis
- 7 Psykiosk
- 9 Introduction Games Hilversum
- 11 Viral Spiral
- 13 Smith and the Storm
- 15 Introduction Games Óbidos
- 17 Blue Brigade
- 19 Puss in Books
- 21 Criminal Feather
- Identification
- 23 Mole Catcher

Cultural Game Prototypes

- 25 Introduction Prototype Games
- 27 Prototypes Aarhus
- 32 Prototypes Hilversum
- 37 Prototypes Óbidos

Expert Interviews

- 42 Dimitri Schuurman
- 43 Stig Børsen Hansen
- 44 Mary Flanagan
- 45 Anneke van Woerden
- 46 Elias Carayannis
- 47 Inês Nunes
- 48 Gaetano Dimita
- 49 Chris Solarski
- 50 Annakaisa Kultima

About EPIC-WE

- 51 About the Project
 - 53 About Cultural Game Jams
-

GAMES THROUGH CULTURE

Games through culture treat cultural heritage and cultural artifacts as primary game-making material and inspiration. They often integrate tangible cultural heritage more or less directly (e.g. a 'Hammershøj horror game' or a game that directly draw on selected artworks or art installations like 'My Filtered Life' using the Rainbow installation at the ARoS Art Museum). They foreground tangible cultural heritage as playable resources, transforming museum objects, nature, archives, buildings, or other cultural artefacts or sites into interactive systems that reinterpret, remix, and materialize culture as new aesthetic and experiential forms.

- **Source material role:** Cultural heritage, artifacts, places, and other sites/artifacts are used as core game-making material rather than background decoration.

- **Aesthetic remediation:** Design emphasizes reimagining, preserving, and artistically re-presenting cultural heritage through mechanics, gameworlds, aesthetics, design.
- **Site-centered making:** Development often takes place within or with specific cultural heritage sites and institutions, enabling direct access to collections and expertise that the groups' game jam with.
- **Interactive reinterpretation:** Games invite players to experience, manipulate, and extend tangible cultural heritage.
- **Local and material specificity:** Strong attachment to place, objects, and particular cultural collections and traditions produces games that are often locally rooted and materially specific.
- **Heritage-focused outcomes:** Games through culture are measured by how the game makes heritage engaging, felt, or newly meaningful to players.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

INTRODUCTION

ARoS

Cultural Game Jams have shown us what becomes possible when people work together across cultures, disciplines, and perspectives: routines are challenged, boundaries dissolve, and new ways of seeing emerge. At ARoS, this collaboration has opened doors to young audiences through a creative format that is both playful and deeply connected to cultural heritage. What begins as a game-making exercise quickly becomes a conversation about art, identity, and the world we share.

Through these Cultural Game Jams, art inspires fresh approaches to game-making —new aesthetics, new gameplay experiences, and new questions about what a game can be emerge from the events. Games, in turn, enrich the cultural sphere by offering participatory, experiential, and empowering modes of engagement that resonate with visitors who seek interaction rather than instruction. They bring an engaging voice to the often “nerdy” and academic nature of museum discourse while maintaining respect for the value and depth of cultural heritage.

Working with the EPIC-WE project has been fun and inspiring, but more importantly, it has revealed the transformative potential of the Cultural Game Jam format. We have witnessed young participants weave threads from art and history into their own narratives, creating games that reflect their hopes, concerns, and visions for cultural heritage and society. Their dedication, curiosity, and generosity of ideas have been a true highlight - demonstrating that when youth engage with cultural heritage, they do so with remarkable cultural awareness, reflection, and creativity.

By inviting participants to view artworks not only as historical artifacts but as raw material for imagination and game-making - we have opened new pathways and spaces for creativity rooted in shared ownership and cultural co-creation. This empowered form of participation fosters deep engagement, reactualises heritage for contemporary relevance, and aligns fully with ARoS's core values of being open, social, and adventurous. It also continues the art world's longstanding tradition of encouraging debate on politics, identity, media, and society - now extended through the language of games through and for culture.

Looking ahead, digitisation and emerging technologies - including AI- will reshape how youth interact with cultural heritage in the future. While these developments bring challenges, they also offer extraordinary possibilities for democratisation, co-creation, and co-ownership. If guided with respect, knowledge, and through playfulness, the future of cultural heritage and cultural engagement may be more participatory and imaginative than ever before.

Cultural Game Jams have only begun to reveal their potential. What we see already through the four jams hosted at ARoS and the twelve jams in the EPIC-WE project is a powerful, joyful model for activating heritage, fostering creativity, and inviting young people to shape the cultural narratives of tomorrow.

Kasper M. Nørmark, project manager at ARoS

FEATURED CULTURAL GAMES

Aarhus

Professional Development of Two Featured Games with Culture

In Aarhus Cultural Hub, the maturation of the selected games, Metamorphosis and 404 Fairness not found – the psykiosk game, followed a structured and value-driven process, combining youth engagement with professional expertise. Both titles were chosen after a collective evaluation and in-depth discussion of candidate projects, where all Aarhus Cultural Hub members prepared notes and assessments in advance.

The development of each game began with a joint start-up meeting involving industry partner Filmby Aarhus, the professional game studio Mothworks, and the participants from the EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam, who made the two prototypes. These meetings created a shared framework of expectations, values, and artistic ambitions. The studio then presented detailed development proposals with clear artistic and technical steps.

Throughout the process, emphasis was placed on linking art and gameplay, ensuring that both games reflect EPIC-WE's ambition to bridge cultural and creative disciplines. This co-creation approach allowed young participants to contribute directly alongside professional developers.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

MOTHWORKS

MOTHWORKS is an independent game studio, creating unique and striking interactive experiences.

Driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition, Mothworks is gonna blow your philosophical, artsy socks off!

They got several projects in the (moth) works.

Team behind Metamorphosis

Hello, we're Puzlerne, the creators behind the core idea of Metamorphosis; the game you now see exhibited at Aros or Filmby Aarhus.

On our team we have a programmer, a storywriter, an artist and a designer, and together we strive to create games that bring people together, give new perspectives and take the world by storm!

Team behind PsyKiosk

We are 404 Fairness Not Found, a group of students at Aarhus University, united by EPIC-WE. Driven by our curiosity and a passion for design, we wanted to create something that makes players think, question, and reflect. Our game Psykiosk is the result of our shared ideas, playful experimentations, and desire to explore moral choices together.

METAMORPHOSIS

A cultural game jam project about identity, discovery, and self love.

Metamorphosis invites the player into a striking visual universe filled with playful interactions with prisms, colors, and markers of identity. The game explores themes such as freedom, identity, and self-confidence. The main character is a small bird, created by Team Puzlerne, symbolizing freedom and the struggle to find it—an image of “learning to fly,” or learning to be oneself.

The player follows the bird through five levels, each representing a step on the journey of self-discovery. Along the way, the bird encounters challenges that can only be overcome by acquiring new abilities and believing in itself. The game begins on the dark, eerie forest floor and ends at the top of a great, colorful, and radiant Tree of Life.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Puzlerne, four young people who participated in the second Cultural Game Jam in Aarhus and later matured in collaboration with the game studio Mothworks.

Mothworks is an independent game studio driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/ac83>

ART X GAME

Metamorphosis is inspired by three artworks from ARoS: Your Condensation by Olafur Eliasson, Marilyn Monroe by Andy Warhol, and House of Dionysus by Sif Itona Westerberg. These works shaped the game's themes and expression—confronting one's own reflection, how colors transform our perception of the world, and the fluidity of identity. The visual style also reflects the artworks: Warhol's color shifts appear in the aesthetics and the character's journey from grey to color, while Westerberg's sculpture inspired the Tree of Life and the ascent from forest floor to treetop.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/3cfd>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Puzlerne are Abtin Amin Marashi, Gaia Elisabeth Mikkelsen, Oliver Oak Stauenberg Orth, and Maren Valentin. They participated in 2024 in a Cultural Game Jam at ARoS in Aarhus, where they created the first prototype of Metamorphosis.

"I've attended many Game Jams before, and when I saw there was one at ARoS, I naturally wanted to join. I'm very interested in both art and games, so this Game Jam was a perfect fit for me," says Maren Valentin.

"It was a combination of my passion for game development and the chance to meet others who share the same interest as me that motivated me to take part," explains Oliver Oak.

The game studio Mothworks joined to further develop Metamorphosis in close collaboration with Team Puzlerne. Based in Aarhus, Mothworks focuses on creating unique, artistic, and eye-catching interactive experiences.

Amalie Kae, director, producer and writer at Mothworks says, *"Taking such direct inspiration from very specific cultural heritage works at ARoS has been a very interesting creative constraint, and we personally think it's made the design of Metamorphosis better."*

PsyKiosk is a point-and-click ethics adventure game that forces players to make difficult ethical choices—only to realize that no matter their actions, the end result is the same. The game provokes thought about fairness, ethics, and the illusion of choice, engaging players in a narrative where ethics is not black and white.

PsyKiosk stands out by using psychological tension in decision-making. Instead of rewarding “good” or “bad” choices, the game highlights moral ambiguity. Through aesthetic and interactive elements, the game distorts the player’s expectations, making them question their own values.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team 404, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Aarhus and the game was later matured in collaboration with the game studio Mothworks. Mothworks is an independent game studio based in Aarhus and driven by innovative narrative design, cutting-edge visuals, and a life-long fascination with the Human Condition.

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/0d72>

Original prototype

FROM ART TO GAME

"Our game was strongly inspired by Jonah Freeman & Justin Lowe's installation Colony Howl. The mix of cultures, the almost post-apocalyptic atmosphere, and the physical feeling of walking through the space really stayed with us. Even the name PsyKiosk comes from the small kiosk in the artwork, combined with the psychedelic atmosphere we felt while exploring the installation." Says Safine Legaard Kastrupsen from the original game jam team, Team 404. The artwork reflects a dystopian, cyberpunk-inspired world that has shaped Team 404's creative vision for the PsyKiosk game.

INTERVIEW

Behind Team 404 are Clara Bille Tvedt, Vilma Lyng Kristensen, Mads Almdal Rasmussen and Safine Legaard Kastrupsen. They participated in 2025 in a Cultural Game Jam at ARoS in Aarhus, where they created the first prototype of PsyKiosk.

"When we developed our idea, we were very focused on the theme of fairness, and on what 'fair' even really means in an unfair world. We wanted the game itself to feel unfair, so that players were pushed to reflect on their own moral choices. Is choosing the 'right' thing still morally right if it leads to a bad outcome? Does intention matter more than the result?" Says Safine.

The game studio Mothworks joined later to develop PsyKiosk further. Mothworks focuses on creating unique and artistic interactive experiences.

Anne Schulin, co-founder and art leader of Mothworks says; "The themes and moral of the original game comes through in a really effective and clever way through the gameplay, and that really excited me about Psykiosk. The core idea is super strong, and that made it fairly straight forward for us as developers to just build on top of what was already there."

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/b904>

FEATURED CULTURAL GAMES

Hilversum

Professional Development of Two Featured Games with Culture

At Hilversum Cultural Hub, we are working on the next step for two games: Viral Spiral and Smith and the Storm. We chose these titles because they are easy to play but also offer something to learn from. Dropstuff made an initial selection. We looked at which projects best fit our way of working: accessible, creative, and with fun as a priority. Afterwards, we presented this to the entire Cultural Hub and made the final choice.

We work in short sprints and simply try things out. Students participate from the beginning, provide feedback, help build, and contribute to improving the games. In addition, we involve other experts in our process, so we can strengthen each other. The atmosphere is open and energetic. Everyone is allowed to speak up or try things out, which makes the process lively. Sometimes things move quickly, sometimes we scrap something, but there is always movement. The games have meanwhile grown considerably: richer in content, more extensive, and simply more fun to play.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

The Creators of Immersive Arts and Interactive Experiences.

DROPSTUFF MEDIA is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences. DROPSTUFF conceptualizes, realizes and presents interactive media projects, audiovisual productions and educational programs for cultural, governmental and commercial partners.

Through exciting new experiences, DROPSTUFF MEDIA translates messages and stories to a broad audience. By applying new techniques we aim to increase public outreach and participation.

Team behind Smith and the Storm

A box of archival photos kicked off Smith and the Storm. On day one we sifted through the images, picked our favourites, and built a collage. The phrase “hotel café restaurant Smit” jumped out, so Mr. Smit became our lead and flooding our theme. We then dug into flood stories and archival visuals online, including the watersnoodramp, and shaped it into an escape room. This game was created by Gabriël Arts, Sanne Houwers, Tristan Bozarov, Duncen Krul, third-year CMD students from the Immersive Design specialisation at Utrecht University of Applied Sciences, who worked together during the 4th EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam in NL.

Team behind Viral Spiral

Viral Spiral was inspired by how quickly fake news spreads, and how important it is to spot what is real. We linked this to EU press freedom because we were curious how anyone can share news, but filtering fakes can also limit that freedom. The team included Beyzanur Aslan, Floor Pasman, Sophie More and Tim Keizer, third-year CMD students at the University of Applied Sciences Amsterdam from the Creative Research Minor, formed for the 3rd EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam in NL.

Viral Spiral

Welcome to Viral Spiral, the board game where you, as an influencer, surf through a whirlwind of real and fake news!

Your feed is overflowing with posts, but not everything can be trusted. It's up to you to separate the facts from the fakes:

Real news? Share it proudly with your followers. Fake news? Report it... or casually swipe it away.

The better your choices, the faster you gain extra followers. Every correct move pushes you further upward, until you reach unprecedented heights.

Make the right call, keep your feed clean, climb to the top, and beat the rest. GO VIRAL!

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team 6, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum. The game was later matured in collaboration with DROPSTUFF MEDIA. DROPSTUFF MEDIA is based in Hilversum, Netherlands and is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/e5ea>

INTERVIEW

Team 6 is Tim, Floor, Beyza and Sophie. They joined the third Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum, Netherlands in April 2024 and developed the original prototype for Viral Spiral.

When asked about the process of developing the game, the team shares: *“The decision to center the game on misinformation and media literacy came from the growing relevance of these issues in today’s society. By making the game interactive and challenging, we wanted players to experience the dilemma of dealing with news they might encounter online.”*

DROPSTUFF MEDIA joined later to further develop the game. Here they share their experience working on the game:

“The development of our game focused on creating a highly topical experience that can evolve over time. We actively involved students in the process, encouraging participation and hands-on data collection. Through continuous iteration, we refined the concept and deliberately involved external participants to generate valuable feedback and improve the overall design.”

GAME INSPIRATION

The game is inspired by a visit to The Mediamuseum in Hilversum. The students say: *“We were inspired by a game focused on media manipulation and fake news and how this influences us. Seeing how media has been used as a tool for propaganda made us think about the power of news in shaping societies and the potential dangers of misinformation. This sparked the idea for Viral Spiral.”* The game aligns with the EU values of democracy, freedom of expression, and access to reliable information. This game serves as a tool for educating players on how misinformation spreads and the consequences of sharing it.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/aaeb>

It is the dead of night. A raging storm lashes the coast and the water keeps rising. Hotel Smith, usually a safe haven for travelers, has become an island of stone and wood, surrounded by churning water. Roads have vanished, dikes have burst. You are trapped together with other guests, scattered across different rooms of the hotel. There is only one hope left: an old emergency transmitter at the reception desk.

Rescue services are heading out, but they don't know who is still trapped here. Only if you can work together to transmit the correct distress signal can a rescue boat reach you before the water floods the hotel. But time is running out. The transmitter is damaged. Information is scattered across different rooms. No single team has everything. Only by working together can you survive.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Orange: Gabriël Arts, Sanne Houwers, Tristan Bozarov, Duncen Krul who took part in the fourth Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum. Later, the game was further developed in collaboration with DROPSTUFF MEDIA. DROPSTUFF MEDIA is based in Hilversum, The Netherlands and is a pioneer in media design and creates immersive and interactive public experiences.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/eade>

GAME INSPIRATION

“A box of archival photos kicked off Smith and the Storm. On day one we sifted through the images, picked our favourites, and built a collage. The phrase “hotel café restaurant Smit” jumped out, so Mr. Smit became our lead and flooding our theme. We then dug into flood stories and archival visuals online, including the watersnoodramp, and shaped it into an escape room,” says Team Orange.

The game incorporates the value of human dignity, as the game is about cooperation between different people even in scary situations. The game focuses on the importance of helping others despite the subtle differences between us.

INTERVIEW

Team Orange joined the fourth Cultural Game Jam in Hilversum, The Netherlands in September 2025 and developed the original prototype for Smith and the Storm.

Here they share the process of developing the prototype:

“Our prototype exists out of a maquette of the entire escape room and a few puzzles to showcase what you would do inside the escape room. We decided to make a maquette of the escape room, to show our vision of how we wanted it to look if we were to ever turn this into a real escape room.”

The game studio DROPSTUFF MEDIA joined later to further develop the game. When asked about their experience of working on the game, they say:

“Our design process focused on making cultural heritage relevant in a contemporary context. The initial ideas and direction were largely driven by students, which we then built upon and further developed. A key challenge was translating these ideas into an engaging game design. Throughout the process, young creators were involved and provided valuable feedback that helped shape and refine the final concept.”

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/6258>

FEATURED CULTURAL GAMES

Óbidos

Professional Development of Four Featured Games with Culture

At Óbidos Cultural Hub, the selection of the two games to be matured (Puss in Books and Criminal Fauna Identification) happened after the second game jam, so that there was a fair amount of time to improve them. The selection process included every Cultural Hub partner, including youth, so that the selected games made sense from every partner's perspective. They should be fun, creative, and culturally relevant/informative, while having direct or indirect commercial potential.

However, some of the games that resulted from the third game jam were acclaimed in those same respects, and there was a feeling of missed opportunity for not including them in the selection. After some analysis by the Cultural Hub's CI partner, BATTLESHEEP, it was decided that two more games could move forward with the maturing process, adding Blue Brigade and Bufo Catcher to the lot.

Given the relatively high quality of the four selected games, BATTLESHEEP decided to enquire the original authors if they would like to be involved in the maturing process, working as game designers, programmers, artists, and audio producers, while receiving professional support and following industry practices. Every participant enthusiastically agreed, as it gave them an opportunity to remain attached to their creations while evolving professionally.

FEATURED GAMES

GAME STUDIO AND JAM TEAMS

BATTLESHEEP is a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, focused on both independent and work-for-hire projects.

Founded as a side-project in 2008 by a team of industry professionals with multi-platform experience, it quickly evolved into an established game studio.

We have released mobile and browser games, ranging from single-player to online multiplayer experiences.

We started out developing casual and advergaming for clients, while simultaneously publishing our own original titles.

More recently we have been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Team behind Blue Brigade

Our jam team was named “Ovo Escalfado” (Poached Egg). A very diverse group of people, each with their specialty. Artists (Daniel Fernandes and Gabriela Branco), programmers (António Rodrigues and Tomás Franco), a concept artist (Lorena Bueno), and a sound designer (Tiago Lourenço).

Team behind Criminal Feather Identification

Hi there! The original team for C.F.I. is made up of a small group of first year students in Lusofona’s Videogames bachelor’s, both artists and programmers, brought together during the second EPIC-WE Cultural Game Jam at Óbidos. Our group included Júlia Costa, João Nogueira, Gabriela Branco, Afonso Cunha, Mariana Martins and António Rodrigues.

Team behind Puss In Books

Hey! We are team “Ovo Cozido” (Boiled Egg) and we created the game Puss in Books! On our team we have just 2 people, a programmer (António) and an artist (Gabriela). Together we love making games and participating in game jams!

Team behind Mole Catcher

Hello! We are “Ovo Estrelado” (Fried Egg), the team behind Mole Catcher. We are composed of a programmer, a pixel artist, and a game designer/pixel character artist, although we all shared some of the game design tasks. We came together by chance and have been working on other projects together since!

Blue Brigade is a small game made by six people, where you play as a PIDE agent during the Portuguese restricting regime, in the town of Óbidos and armed with the regime's iconic blue pencil. At first, it feels light and playful as you run around censoring people who break the rules.

But as you notice the banned clothes, forbidden music, and silenced conversations, the tone shifts, and the village begins to lose its colors. Behind the cute art and simple tasks, the game quietly shows the weight of living under censorship.

GAME CREATORS

The game was originally created by Team Ovo Escalfado, six young people who participated in the third Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos and it was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/cca6>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Ovo Escalfado (Poached Egg) are Daniel Fernandes, Gabriela Branco, António Rodrigues, Tomás Franco, Lorena Bueno and Tiago Lourenço. When asked about the experience Daniel says: *“An exciting teamwork project that allowed us to develop a remarkable game while also learning a lot about Óbidos’ culture and history.”*

“A funny and at times stressful project that really pushed our creativity, with stretchy character animations that gave the whole game a unique, quirky charm,” explains António.

“A cute and ironic art style packed with earthy tones, sketchy line art, and round characters that make up for the realistic historic time and tough situation it presents,” says Lorena.

The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop the game. Nélío Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: *“It’s incredible that a game with this depth and charm was the product of a game jam. It is challenging and fun to play, it looks amazing, and has layers of details that you unveil only through multiple playthroughs.”*

GAME INSPIRATION

When the theme of the game jam was announced, the Carnation Revolution of 1974, a lot of ideas immediately came to mind. A knight wielding a black censor bar and hitting people with it to censor them. As the theme was explored more closely and the historical context was examined, the ideas shifted toward something more authentic. Instead of a censor bar, the tool actually used at the time, the blue pencil, was introduced, making it fitting for the player to take the role of an agent from that era. Further research into the period revealed what people were forbidden to talk about, the clothing styles that were banned, and the music and books that were censored.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/78f7>

In Puss In Books, you embark on a journey guiding a kitty through a whimsical journey as it explores dreams inspired by Óbidos' legends. Traverse a literary world and craft an enchanting narrative as the cat travels through the captivating scenarios within its dreams.

Experience a blend of imagination and adventure, where each dream unveils new challenges and discoveries in a quest to uncover the essence of literary magic. With this game, we hope to offer a small taste of Óbidos through typography, books, and hopefully cats!

GAME CREATORS

The original prototype game was created by Team Ovo Cozido, two young people who took part in the first Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos, in February 2024. Puss In Books was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/3f96>

INTERVIEW

Behind Team Ovo Cozido are António Rodrigues, a programmer, and Gabriela Branco, an artist. They participated in 2024 in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos under the theme “Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature,” where they created the first prototype of Puss In Books.

When asked about the experience António says: *“It was a lot of fun to work on and to visit the town and to make a small cozy game about a cat living through stories.”*

Gabriela continues, *“Óbidos was an inspiring experience we will carry for life.”*

The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop Puss In Books. BATTLESHEEP have released mobile and browser games, ranging from single-player to online multiplayer experiences. Nélío Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: *“Living proof of what a small, talented team can accomplish in a very short time with the right focus. Being so content-heavy, this was a risky project to do in a game jam context. Yet here it is for everyone to experience.”*

GAME INSPIRATION

The game takes inspiration from Scribblenauts and the way its puzzles interact with the environment around the player. The idea came from an excursion trip to Óbidos, where a visit to a typography shop included an introduction to the craft of printing and the process of imprinting shapes and letters onto paper. This inspired the idea for a writing game. While strolling around Óbidos and seeing kitty after kitty in the streets, lying in stores and at libraries, the main character had to be a kitty. The current version of the game took inspiration from the Óbidos legend "Door of Betrayal".

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/e9a2>

In the Óbidos Lagoon, several crimes occur throughout the year. From stealing someone's precious items to well-prepared murder scenes. The culprits? Birds! Play as a detective and find out who did the atrocities in the case files. Arrest those feathery criminals and earn yourself a promotion!

This game was made with the objective of offering, through some ridiculous designs and laidback aesthetics, a way to teach or promote interest in the lagoon's fauna and other dynamics within this ecosystem.

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Júlia Costa, João Nogueira, Gabriela Branco, Afonso Cunha, Mariana Martins and António Rodrigues. Six young people who participated in the second Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos. The game was later matured in collaboration with BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal, that has recently been working on educational, serious, and casino games for domestic and international clients.

Original prototype

YOU WERE WRONG.

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/d37b>

INTERVIEW

The team behind Criminal Feather Identification participated in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos in 2024, where they created the first prototype originally called Criminal Fauna Identification. When asked about the process of developing the game the team says: *“The Óbidos Game Jam was an unforgettable experience! Turning birds into characters was an interesting adventure, making them look somewhat resembling a criminal while keeping them true to their living counterparts was a captivating challenge,”* says João. Mariana continues, *“The jam was an experience that I wouldn't have the opportunity to have at any other time. I was inexperienced then, but participating pushed me and helped me build a habit to keep creating. I felt much more confident in my skills, which enabled me to have fun finishing this project.”* The game studio BATTLESHEEP joined later to further develop the game. *“A lot of research went into this game, with the team pushing hard to keep it playful, funny, informative, and replayable. The true meaning of team effort and dedication,”* says Nélio Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP.

GAME INSPIRATION

The main inspiration was a game called “Time Waster”, where you have to connect simplified crime descriptions to mugshots of human criminals. The theme of the Cultural Game Jam was “Óbidos Lagoon”, and who better represents it than its residents, the avifauna? In the game, all the criminals are native birds from the Óbidos Lagoon. Following their habits and lifestyle, they perform crimes inspired by their way of living and eating habits. All suspects in the game were kept as birds to make it harder to dismiss the innocent ones. The game “Papers, Please” was also an inspiration, in the way the information is presented to the player through different files.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/47e9>

Mole Catcher

parked at B5.

Last summer I went to... (password)
 Where are you located?
 What's your code name?
 Where did you park?

You are transported back to 1974 Portugal, which is under the regime of a dictatorship. You are stationed in the small town of Óbidos as a revolutionary tasked with keeping check of who enters the village's iconic theatre, which is home to a crucial meeting for the upcoming revolution, meant to overthrow the dictatorship!

However, you are informed that moles are trying to infiltrate the meeting. It is your job to check documents and compare information to find out who the moles are!

DEVELOPERS

The game was originally created by Team Ovo Estrelado, four young people who took part in the third Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos. Behind Team Ovo Estrelado are Cátia Nascimento, Maria Sequeira, Júlia Costa and Tiago Lourenço. Mole Catcher was later matured in collaboration with the game studio BATTLESHEEP, a game development studio based in Lisbon, Portugal.

Original prototype

Access the prototype
<https://lnk.dk/8623>

INTERVIEW

Team Ovo Estrelado participated in a Cultural Game Jam in Óbidos in 2025, where they created the first prototype of Mole Catcher, originally called Bufo Catcher. When asked about the process of developing the game the team says: “Everything in the playable area was idealized with the intent of making the player feel like they were truly living that role of a guard in 1974,” says Cátia. “To truly immerse the player, we tried our best to find real-life information that was used at the time,” says Maria. “We wanted to convey to the player the sense of secrecy and fear the Portuguese people faced during the harsh years of the Estado Novo,” Júlia says. “The worry of being constantly watched and spied on and that every action you took might get judged by an authority and even get you arrested.” Later in the process the game studio BATTLESHEEP joined to further develop the game. Nélio Codices, co-founder and director of BATTLESHEEP says: “Disguised as a simple game, this is a true gem of an idea. Shedding light on true events, it particularly speaks to the hearts of those who lived through the Portuguese regime and, later, the revolution.”

GAME INSPIRATION

The theme behind the Cultural Game Jam was the Portuguese Carnation Revolution and the jam took place in the town of Óbidos. That was a good opportunity to make the game be set in the town and highlight this aspect of the preparations for the revolution that has been overshadowed and is widely unknown. The main inspiration was the game “Papers, Please”, as that was the best format to show military artifacts and objects of that time and the grime and overwhelming pressure that was felt during the dictatorship. “Small nods to the time in which the game took place, were the artistic choices in things like, for example, the character sprites, whose artistic direction was inspired by the colors and proportions used by famous Portuguese painters who lived through the dictatorship,” says Maria Sequeira.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/3288>

INTRODUCTION

THE CULTURAL GAME PROTOTYPES

During the EPIC-WE project we have hosted **12 Cultural Game Jams** - 4 from the Óbidos Cultural Hub in Portugal, 4 from the Hilversum Cultural Hub in the Netherlands, and 4 from the Aarhus Cultural Hub in Denmark.

Here, **424 young people** (between 15-25) have worked together in teams to create **108 Cultural Game Prototypes**. Either as **games through culture** - working directly with culture as material for game-making - or as **games for culture** - exploring or interpreting heritage and values through game-making that aim for critical reflection, civic engagement, or cultural transformation.

From these cultural game prototypes each Cultural Hub selected two or more of the teams games to be further developed into a featured game with culture through close collaboration between youth and the three Cultural Hub's game studios - showing how games working with culture can play a role in co-creating new futures in the intersection of games, heritage, values, and culture. In total 8 Featured EPIC-WE Games was developed during the project.

For the EPIC-WE Legacies Event a broad selection of the 108 Cultural Game Prototypes has been curated by each

Cultural Hub to be showcased at ARoS Art Museum and Filmby Aarhus as one of the big legacies of the project. For the Games through Culture EXPO at ARoS Art Museum, 18 games were selected and showcased and for the Games for Culture EXPO at Filmby Aarhus, 20 games were selected and showcased.

This is the legacy of young people taking up game-making as a form of culture-making - the result of which you find in this EXPO Catalogue. The EXPO Catalogue contains and presents all the showcased Cultural Game Prototypes along with the 8 Featured Games. Together they illustrate the power of young people's cultural-creative thinking with heritage and values and the potential of Cultural Game Jams inviting young people to game jam with cultural heritage themes, sites, collections, archives, artworks, values, and identities.

In this catalogue we celebrate all of the young people that is the beating and empowered heart of our epic-we - we hope they inspire you like they have inspired us!

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

PROTOTYPE GAMES

Aarhus

- 27 GRIND THE WORLD
- 27 GOOSE ON THE LOOSE
- 28 ROOMINATION
- 28 MUSEUM OF DREAMS
- 31 CREATE YOUR LEGACY
- 31 PLAYING GOD
- 32 YOUR FILTERED LIFE

Hilversum

- 32 THE CHANCE OF YOUR LIFE
- 35 CYBER CRISIS
- 35 RIGGED RAILS
- 36 THE OTTER SIDE
- 36 THE NEIGHBOURS

Óbidos

- 37 WALLS OF COLOR
- 37 IN SEARCH FOR WORDS
- 38 MOIRA'S HEX
- 38 HE MUST BE FED
- 41 CONQUISTA
- 41 DEADMAN CRAWLING

GRIND THE WORLD

Created by: Mikkel Ugilt, Kostya Milkevich and Victoria Elle Bache

Inspired by: Hanne Nielsen & Birgit Johnsen's video performance 'Peeling Onions' (1995)

Building on: Freedom

Grind disturbing items or refuse.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/9621>

From household objects to a puppy or a baby, this thought-provoking game asks the player to grind increasingly disturbing items.

The game explores ethical decisions in gameplay: Players have the freedom to refuse, making them reflect on mindless gaming behavior and the consequences of their actions.

GOOSE ON THE LOOSE

Created by: William, Noah, Liv and Lucas

Inspired by: Johannes Larsen's painting 'Ten Brent Geese on the Shore' (1921)

Buidling on: Freedom

Immerse yourself in childlike imagination.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/8b7d>

We have aimed to create a sense of peace, albeit through the eyes of a goose. A relaxing world to truly immerse yourself in, with fun gameplay and the freedom to move wherever you want. Establishing the feeling of a free world and a free imagination, Goose on the Loose incorporates small elements of philosophy and a calming atmosphere.

ROOMINATION

Created by: Oscar, Soren and Adem

Inspired by: Vilhelm Hammershøi's paintings in 'the exhibition 'Human Nature' (1889-1911)

Building on: Freedom

Even when you are close to freedom, you can't always reach it.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/b7e6>

With inspiration from the Danish painter Vilhelm Hammershøi, celebrated for his poetic portraits and interiors, 'Roomination' sets a tranquil scene in atmospheric environments reminiscent of his art and color palette. Experience the interplay of light and shadow, contemplate about solitude, and discover the beauty of everyday moments.

MUSEUM OF DREAMS

Created by: Morten, Peter, Mikkel, Nicolai and Victor

Inspired by: The entire 'Human Nature'-exhibition.

Building on: Equality and freedom

Break the rules and remix culture.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/6d3a>

A virtual reality sandbox game where players shrink to child-size in a surreal museum and remix artworks using paint guns and stickers. Inspired by European art history, players break museum rules through an empowering gameplay that challenges who get to "touch" cultural heritage, making it playful, inclusive, and co-creative.

CULTURAL GAME JAMS AARHUS

CULTURAL GAME JAMS AARHUS

CREATE YOUR LEGACY

Created by: Maha Farid Majid, Tomasnuclear, Maja Børsting Lund, Mark Oliver Sandfeld Nielsen, Beinta Brynhildardóttir Egholm and Rikke Gehrke Jensen

Inspired by: Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Århus 31 May 1849' (1853)

Building on: Freedom

Who shapes history and cultural heritage?

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/da6d>

In this game you interact with Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Aarhus 31 May 1849'. You play as an artist risking your life while sketching cavalries fighting, overlooking the battlefield, dodging bullets and swords; while painting an art piece you hope to become your future legacy, and a testament to your heroic act.

PLAYING GOD

Created by: Patrekur Agnarsson and Aimo Hirvonen

Inspired by: Jørgen Sonne's painting 'Cavalry Skirmish near Århus 31 May 1849' (1853)

Building on: Equality and freedom

Play God in a war simulation inspired by Danish art history.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/e3f2>

A simulated battleground augmented reality game where you decide which side wins by playing God by moving soldiers, giving them weapons, or eliminating them. Inspired by Jørgen Sonne's iconic war painting, the game transforms your surroundings into a Danish-Prussian battlefield, exploring themes of equality and divine intervention in war.

YOUR FILTERED LIFE

Created by: Maria, August, Mathilde and Marthea

Inspired by: Olafur Eliasson's 'Your Rainbow Panorama' (2011)

Building on: Equality and freedom

Make the right decisions and shape your future!

You've just turned 18 and gained your independence. Every choice matters, some small, some life-changing. Our game explores themes of equality and freedom through roleplay, highlighting how both personal choices and the luck of one's starting position shape opportunities, just like in real life.

THE CHANCE OF YOUR LIFE

Created by: Team The Chance of Your Life

Inspired by: 'The Propaganda Game' in the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Building on: Social inequalities

Fight your way up against social inequalities.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/a992>

A strategic board game for 2-4 players that explores self-development, technological progress, and societal inequality. Players embody unique characters, each with different starting advantages, as they earn Self Development Points (ZOP) by making choices and overcoming obstacles. The first to reach 800 ZOP and return to the center wins.

CULTURAL GAME JAMS HILVERSUM

CULTURAL GAME JAMS HILVERSUM

CYBER CRISIS

Created by: Daan Koekkoek, Kaj-Benjamin Sitanala and Ryan Vries

Inspired by: Archive clips from the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision

Building on: Human dignity

A fast-paced card game where players battle a powerful Phone.

Access the game <https://lnk.dk/52c7>

A strategic role-playing card game tackling cyberbullying and digital fairness. Players face off against a formidable Phone that wields their past online actions as weapons. Blending strategy and chance, the game explores the impact of digital interactions while reinforcing EU values like dignity and responsible communication.

RIGGED RAILS

Created by: Team 4

Inspired by: Inclusion of meaningful choices

Building on: Equality and human rights

What if we're all on the same train, but in different classes?

Access the game <https://lnk.dk/1beb>

'Rigged Rails' is a board game about class conflict, where players race to first class on a train while facing an unfair system. Earn money through luck, work, or crime, but beware: your character's background determines how easy the journey will be.

THE OTTER SIDE

Created by: Team Otterbende
Inspired by: Gamedesign in the Netherlands
Institute for Sound and Vision
Building on: Empathy and environmental responsibility

A game of otters struggling against human-made threats to find a safe habitat.

A luck-based board game where players experience the struggles of endangered European otters. Facing pollution, habitat loss, and human dangers, they must collect resources to survive. The game raises awareness of environmental protection and highlights gaps in EU policies, urging players to rethink the role of nature in governance.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/464d>

THE NEIGHBOURS

Created by: Team De Buren
Inspired by: Loneliness among the elderly
Building on: Human dignity

Fight elderly loneliness through small but meaningful actions.

Brighten the lives of senior citizens through thoughtful interactions! Players earn emotional points by performing acts of kindness, such as sharing a meal, arranging visits, or fostering connections between elderly characters. By engaging with personal stories and unique needs, players develop empathy and understanding.

Access the game
<https://lnk.dk/14da>

WALLS OF COLOR

Created by: Júlia Costa, Rodrigo Marques and Sónia Raposo

Inspired by: The town of Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature.

Building on: Cultural preservation

Keep Óbidos pristine by stopping tourists from defacing its walls.

Óbidos is a breathtaking town with a beautiful castle, vast brick walls, and white houses with intense blue accents. However, tourists keep painting on the walls! Your job is simple: clean and prevent tourists from rubbing blue paint on the white walls. Keep the village pristine and beautiful.

IN SEARCH FOR WORDS

Created by: Eduardo Rocha, Gonçalo Sampaio, Hugo Silva, Leonardo Henrique and Tomás Cardoso

Inspired by: The town of Óbidos, UNESCO Creative City of Literature

Building on: Cultural preservation

Will you get through the awful writer's block? Or will you let your imagination be taken away by this greedy screenbound world?

Overcome writer's block in this magical platformer inspired by Óbidos, a historic medieval town in Portugal. Help Joaquim, a rich and famous Portuguese writer with writer's block, collect special Metal Letters, regain his lost imagination, discover the magic word, and overcome his struggle.

MOIRA'S HEX

Created by: João Rodrigues and Lee Dias

Inspired by: Óbidos legends "Cova da Moira" and "Bicho do Vau"

Building on: Freedom

Defy the curse, snuff the lamps, reclaim your freedom, but don't let the Bicho do Vau hear you.

A stealth horror game combining Óbidos legends "Cova da Moira" and "Bicho do Vau". As a village resident cursed by the Enchanted Moira, you're trapped within Óbidos' walls. Venture beyond the boundaries to snuff out 5 oil lamps and lift the curse, while avoiding the lurking Bicho do Vau that hunts anyone who makes loud noises in the shadowy forest.

HE MUST BE FED

Created by: André Leandro, António Rodrigues, Gabriela Branco, Mafalda Cavaco and Vera Nunes

Inspired by: Óbidos legend "Covão dos Musaranhos"

Building on: Freedom

Catch some fish. Feed the Musaranho. Survive the night.

A horror-suspense 3D fishing simulator based on the Óbidos Musaranho legend. As a newcomer fisherman, you must catch fish to feed the strange forest deity in exchange for village peace. Begin each day by fishing beneath shifting skies, check your progress on the scale, and place your catch on the altar at dusk. Ring the bell and await what answers from the dark.

CULTURAL GAME JAMS ÓBIDOS

A CONQUISTA

Created by: Isaac Pais, Pedro Gouveia, Tiago Patrício, Carolina Correia, Tiago Félix and Lourenço Rosário
Inspired by: Óbidos legend "Porta da Traição"
Building on: Freedom

Experience the human cost of war, freedom and trust through this classical tragedy retelling.

"A Conquista" is a narrative-focused adventure game exploring the Óbidos legend "Porta da Traição" (The Door of Betrayal). Infiltrate the Moor-occupied castle during its historical siege, build relationships with residents, and find a way to open the town's doors from inside.

DEADMAN CRAWLING

Created by: Cátia Nascimento, Maria Sequeira, Afonso Cunha, Lisa Carvalho, Júlia Costa, David Mendes and Daniel Fernandes
Inspired by: Óbidos legend "Covão dos Musaranhos"
Building on: Freedom

Crawl through the caves and survive the Musaranho!

A 3D pixel horror game based on the Óbidos Musaranho legend. A fisherman and his group encounter a mysterious creature at a calm lake and flee to cave systems. In this cat-and-mouse dynamic, crawl through dark caves, use sound to navigate, and avoid the terrifying Musaranho while searching for an escape route back home.

Empowering Innovation: Living Labs and Youth Participation

Interview with Dimitri Schuurman

Expert Member of EPIC-
WE Advisory Board

Visiting Professor Gent University – Business Developer imec-MICT-UGent – Senior Research Strategist ENoLL. Dimitri Schuurman is an expert in Living Labs, innovation management, co-creation, co-design, and user innovation, particularly in the context of emerging technologies.

EPIC-WE have seen the full inclusion of our Youth Advisory Members into decision-making and creation processes. Does this integration of Youth align with the envisioned multi-stakeholder model of Living Labs?

By involving Youth on an organisational level, the project is taking an important step forward. One key consideration is the extent to which the Youth members will be involved: will they be motivated to shape the strategic direction of the project, or will they be more interested in short-term participation?, he asks. Regardless, the approach is innovative, whether it succeeds or faces challenges, as the insights can benefit future initiatives.

And does it have the potential to enhance the project's impact?

Undoubtedly. It is essential that Youth members have a seat at the table, are treated equally, and have an equal voice in decision-making. Their motivation to stay involved can be seen as a key indicator of whether true empowerment has

been achieved. In this sense, disengagement would have to lead to reassessment of the approach, to understand what changes are needed to ensure everyone feels valued and included in EPIC-WE.

EPIC-WE is committed to cross-sectoral collaborations, and so, the project welcomes strategies for more unified and synergistic approaches. Are there any strategies or insights of special relevance?

One effective strategy he highlights is organising offline events where participants are grouped into multidisciplinary teams and given tasks or discussion topics in a playful and engaging environment. Another effective method can be to use design-based approaches, in which groups work together to create something tangible. Providing participants with alternative ways to express themselves (such as through drawing, building, or designing) can foster mutual understanding and ensure that everyone contributes.

“When working with Youth members, their role changes drastically when they are referred to as “experts on the needs and wants of Youth”, instead of simply ‘young people’.”

Ethical Youth Engagement in EPIC-WE

Interview with Stig Børsen Hansen

Expert member of EPIC-
WE Advisory Board

Stig Børsen Hansen is the external ethics advisor to EPIC-WE. Hansen brings invaluable expertise, helping us in our commitment as well as practice to involve young people in a recognised and fair manner throughout EPIC-WE.

A balancing act: 'codified' and 'experiential' ethics

"Teaching ethics involves navigating two distinct dimensions," Hansen explains. *"Firstly, there are the codifiable aspects: informed consent, security of data, clear communication, and intellectual property rights. These can, and should be, explicitly taught."* However, ethics go far beyond the 'codifiable'. There is a less tangible dimension that is crucial here, which is more "fine-grained and experiential" but it is just as important as the more straightforward elements in ethical practices.

Ethical considerations in youth engagement

"Young people, especially teenagers, can and should have a say in consent processes." His main advice on this is to ensure that communication is clear, and always in dialogue, and also to be conscious of understanding and respecting young people's capabilities.

Creating spaces for genuine expression

To ethically involve youth, Hansen recommends establishing conditions that are conducive for authentic feedback and expression. *"It's important to have forums where young people can freely express their thoughts, including subversive or playful feedback,"* he suggests. Hansen emphasises paying close attention to youth voices and behaviours that may indicate dissent, boredom, or disagreement, as these can provide valuable insights into ethical engagement and reflection.

Recognition and fairness as cornerstones

While researchers and institutions are getting something they need from the interact with young participants, we should also ask: *"Are youths getting something valuable out of this engagement, such as professional networks, academic credits, or certificates?"* and he adds that we should be genuinely open to their own ideas about what they could get out of their participation.

"Being ethical researchers means continually adjusting our practices through reflection and open conversation. By genuinely listening to and respecting young people, EPIC-WE can ensure ethical integrity and meaningful participation."

Designing for Values

Interview with Mary Flanagan

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

A game designer, researcher, artist, and founder of Tiltfactor Lab at Dartmouth College, Mary is a pioneer in value-centred game design. As a member of our Advisory Board, she continues to help us explore how values and culture can intersect meaningfully through game-making.

More Than Just a Game: Putting Values at the Center

Flanagan's work revolves around a simple yet transformative idea: games are cultural artifacts. And as such, they express values. *"The important thing,"* Flanagan explains, *"is that values don't have to be abstract. We can treat them like design challenges. What does caring look like in a game? What does freedom of expression mean as a mechanic? These become starting points for creativity."*

Making Cultural Values Tangible

While values are often easy to discuss, culture can be more elusive, especially when the goal is to create games that express shared European identities or heritage. *"It's hard to talk about 'culture' without drifting into abstraction. That's why facilitators need tools, examples, and ways to ground the conversation."* Start with real cultural references and encourage participants to remix them by modifying a known game imagining a new one, or drawing storyboards.

Centering the Process, Not Just the Product

A recurring theme in Mary's work, and a core value of EPIC-WE, is the importance of the process. In value-based game design, it's not about shipping a flawless game. It's about what happens along the way: the conversations, the decisions, the reflections. *"Community, values, and ideation are central to the process,"* she explains. *"It's critical that your evaluation captures that – not just the game at the end."*

Designing for Empowerment and Agency

Beyond cultural values and inclusivity, EPIC-WE also aims to nurture a sense of agency in young participants. Flanagan believes game-making is uniquely positioned to do just that. *"Game creation gives people the chance to shape systems, make choices, and tell their own stories,"* she says. But it must be approached thoughtfully. Her advice: make sure everyone has a meaningful role. Offer collaborative challenges with no single "winner."

"Think about what you want the experience to feel like. How do you want participants to see themselves afterward? That's where empowerment begins."

Creativity, Community, and the Power of Process

Interview with Anneke Van Woerden

Expert Member of EPIC-WE Advisory Board

With a background that bridges cultural studies, experience design, and social innovation, Anneke brings deep insight into community-based creative processes. Her leadership in initiatives like the Global Goals Jam, and her expertise in learning and facilitation, make her a vital contributor to our shared mission.

The Process Over the Prototype

One of Anneke's key insights is a shift in mindset: from product to process. *"In the early days, we were focused on outcomes — on building something tangible by the end of a jam. But over time, we realized the real magic happens in the collaboration itself,"* she says. *"The conversations, the negotiations, the collective understanding of a challenge — that's where change starts."*

Creating Space for Creativity for everyone

"Creativity flourishes when people feel seen and heard. That's why trust-building, even if it feels like a soft skill, is essential." She also pushes back against narrow ideas of creativity: *"Brainstorming sessions can be great, but they often favour extroverts. We need to embrace a diversity of methods — visual, written, silent reflection — to make sure everyone's voice is heard."*

Embracing Diversity—Locally and Globally

EPIC-WE's Cultural Hubs each approach European values through different lenses. Anneke sees this as a strength. *"When you allow each hub to lean into its unique context, surprising commonalities emerge,"* she notes. *"Sometimes it's by starting local that you end up discovering shared values."* She adds: *"We offered a framework, but local hosts are the experts of their context. That's where the magic happens."*

Human Connection as the Core

Throughout the conversation, Anneke returns again and again to one central theme: human connection. *"At the start of building the GGJ community, I spent hours on one-on-one calls. That personal connection laid the groundwork for everything,"* she says. *"Even as we scaled, we tried to keep that sense of closeness — through local ambassadors, annual webinars, or sharing stories from past jams."*

"Don't underestimate the power of coming together—with trust, creativity, and the courage to ask better questions."

The power of helical frameworks

Interview with Elias Carayannis

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

Dr. Elias G. Carayannis is a Full Professor of Science, Technology, Innovation, and Entrepreneurship at The George Washington University School of Business. In 2009-10 he co-created the Quadruple Helix concept and later expanded it to the Quintuple Helix, incorporating environmental sustainability to drive growth and resilience.

How has the quadruple helix evolved, and what does it mean for current projects like EPIC-WE?

Since the '90s, there has been an emphasis on fostering public-private partnerships for research and technology advancement. The triple helix concept emerged, focusing on collaboration among governments, universities, and industries. However, this model primarily benefitted elites, leaving out broader societal participation. This imbalance led me to develop the quadruple helix, which adds civil society to the equation, ensuring that innovation and resource allocation include a wider array of voices and perspectives. The quadruple helix model incorporates civil society, ensuring transparency, representation, and empowerment for all individuals, especially those directly impacted by environmental issues.

What challenges have you encountered in fostering collaboration across diverse stakeholder groups?

Effective collaboration often faces challenges due to diverse expertise and perspectives. For examples, in a UN project on intangible cultural heritage, diverse backgrounds led to communication barriers and misalignment. This highlighted the need for a shared language and common understanding. I coined the paradox of converging disciplines and diverging specializations to describe this. It's critical to use mixed methods—qualitative and quantitative—to develop a shared language of thought.

How can we integrate youth into the quadruple helix framework effectively?

Youth are a vital part of civil society, bringing unique perspectives and longer time horizons. Engaging them requires understanding their thoughts, aspirations, fears, and expectations. It's essential to build consensus and involve them in co-creating a shared vision. Projects like EPIC-WE need to cultivate a common language that resonates with both older and younger generations, fostering unity and collaboration.

“In essence, our goal is to foster an environment where all stakeholders are co-creators, actively engaged in shaping the outcome. This approach ensures that our initiatives are not only effective but also sustainable and inclusive.”

Giving youth the power to shape culture

Interview with Inês Nunes

Expert Member of EPIC-WE Youth Advisory Board

Inês Nunes is a student and researcher in neuropsychology and communication sciences, specialising in serious games for rehabilitation. She brings a critical perspective to EPIC-WE's mission of empowering young Europeans to shape culture through imagination, game design, and cultural heritage.

Cultural Game Jams: acts of encounter and (re)discovering

The Cultural Game Jams lie at the heart of EPIC-WE, it is where safe spaces are created for young people to reinterpret local and European heritage through game-making. Inês points to the transformative potential of the game jams, and how they have revealed hidden or forgotten layers of familiar as well as unfamiliar heritage. *“Sometimes it feels like we’re rediscovering our own culture. The themes—like the Óbidos Lagoon or the 25th of April Revolution—have given us the freedom to be creative, to reflect on the past, and to connect it to our future.”*

Learning by leading: giving up control

As a facilitator in the game jams, Inês became very much aware of the delicate balance between guiding and influencing, especially when working with youth: *“It’s always a concern—so you need to ask yourself: am I forcing a perspective?”*

she explains, *“I prefer letting participants explore the theme from their own point of view.”*

Inspiring tangible impact in local communities

Inês sees clear signs that EPIC-WE is making a lasting difference in her community. From learning about endangered professions like traditional booksellers to discovering that the Óbidos lagoon is a UNESCO property, the project has sparked real-world engagement. *“Young people started to realise that their actions have an impact. We’re not just preserving culture—we’re living it.”* And when the game jam explored the 25th of April, Portugal’s Freedom Day, it prompted profound reflection on active citizenship, democracy and human rights. *“We have to make sure our actions today keep us from going back to the past. That’s the power of this project—it connects the past, present, and future.”*

“Try. We all have something to say. At the very least, you’ll find someone willing to listen to your story.”

Aspects of game creation

Interview with Gaetano Dimita

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

Gaetano Dimita is a Reader in Interactive Entertainment and Intellectual Property (IP) Law at the Centre for Commercial Law Studies (CCLS), Queen Mary University of London. Gaetano contributes to EPIC-WE by exploring how legal frameworks influence game creation and gameplay experiences.

How has the video game industry approached supporting community creativity, and what legal challenges do creators face in monetizing and protecting their work?

The video game industry has been relatively proactive in supporting community creativity compared to other industries. Over time, user license agreements evolved, with some offering broad freedoms for creative works as long as they adhered to certain guidelines. Others are much stricter, claiming ownership over user creations or requiring perpetual, royalty-free licenses for any derivative works. This uncertainty extends to modern platforms like YouTube and Twitch, where creators build livelihoods through “let’s play” videos or streams. Many digital creators do not fully understand the implications of their actions or how to safeguard their creative output.

How can we empower creators with the right tools and knowledge from the very beginning of a Cultural Game Jam?

During Cultural Game Jams, creators should learn how licenses define usage rights—whether the license is perpetual, global, or restricted—and that they retain moral rights even after licensing. For instance, they can object if someone alters their work in ways that violate its integrity or removes their name as the creator. These are fundamental principles, and while creators don’t need to master every legal detail, they should grasp the basics to protect their creations.

How can creators navigate the complexities of intellectual property, contracts, and profit sharing to ensure fair compensation and long-term success?

Divide the roles and document it: It’s important to recognize that there are different roles and expertise required when scaling a project, and no one person can master everything.

Know when to call a lawyer and know it can be free: These considerations also depend on the type of contract the creators have. Having legal counsel during negotiations is invaluable.

“If we want to build a sustainable creative economy, it is essential to educate creators on their copyright and legal rights, so that they can protect and monetize their work effectively.”

Imagination in Motion:

What can a game teach us about ourselves?

Interview with Chris Solarski

Expert Member of EPIC-
WE Advisory Board

Chris Solarski, a game designer, artist, and educator, about this and other topics. His work combines movement, storytelling, and visual design. In addition, Solarski is an important member of the EPIC-WE project as part of the project's Advisory Board

From Michelangelo to Mario

Solarski's story started in game development, working as an artist at Sony, but he soon found himself pulled toward other forms of art, including figurative drawing, gesture, and the emotional weight of form. He began exploring how the principles of painting and sculpture could shape not only the visuals of games but also their design, mechanics, and even the way we move through them. For him, this process did not only enrich his understanding but also led to the development of his first book, *Drawing Basics and Video Game Art*. Have you ever wondered what Michelangelo and Mario have in common?

Embodiment and empathy

One of the key ideas that Solarski shared with us was the concept of embodiment, whereby players of video games experience the illusion that something in the game is part of their body, or vice versa.

When asked how this capacity for imagination could be developed within EPIC-WE, Solarski described a workshop in which participants were asked to draw their signatures as large as possible on a sheet of paper and then swap with someone else to trace their signature. Through this exercise, people began to recognise differences in movement, identifying what felt fluid or tense, familiar or strange. It became clear that design is not just visual, but something that is felt. Furthermore, Solarski shared his thoughts with us on the role of empathy. According to Solarski, “when we talk about empathy-driven design, it’s not just about fostering positive emotions – it’s about truly understanding and connecting with the diverse realities of others, including those in the context of disability, gender identity, and other lived experiences. This is also where games stand out as an art form. They have a unique capacity to allow us to embody not only a wide variety of people but also objects”.

***“One idea was to take an ordinary game, such as table tennis, and play it with a completely different object, such as a basketball. This way, the game breaks, and players need to adapt and start thinking creatively.*”**

Shaping culture through games

Interview with Annakaisa Kultima

Expert member of EPIC-WE advisory board

Scholar in Game Studies and long-time game jam organiser. Annakaisa has taken part in over 60 game jams—as participant, creator, judge, and organiser. Combining research with practice, she shapes EPIC-WE’s approach to creativity, learning, and cultural exploration.

A living culture of game jams

“One of my first rules for organising a game jam,” Annakaisa shares, “is to understand the local culture of game jams. Expectations vary depending on history, geography, and who’s participating.” EPIC-WE’s mission is to empower youth to explore European values and heritage through games, but “there’s no one-size-fits-all model—especially when it comes to Cultural Game Jams.” Game jams are, she explains, “a living culture,” shaped by context and collaboration. “Some jams are competitive, some are reflective, some prioritise polished products, others focus on the learning process.”

Managing expectations through process

Institutions often use game jams to explore topics like health or heritage. But Annakaisa stresses the need to align goals: “Are we aiming for polished, playable games—or are we creating a space for participatory design, where learning and engagement come first?”

Creativity needs care

Annakaisa advocates for safe, collaborative environments. “Collaboration beats competition,” she says. Mid-jam presentations help: “Participants are often anxious on day one. If you create a space where helping each other is the norm, creativity flourishes.”

Game-making is for everyone

A core belief in Annakaisa’s work is that anyone can contribute to game-making—no matter their background or skillset. Whether you are a poet, historian, or teenager with no coding experience, accessible tools like Bitsy or Twine allow anyone to jump in and create. “There’s still a myth that you need a programmer and an artist to make a game,” she says. “It’s just not true anymore. Game creation is a powerful, democratic medium—and the barriers to entry are lower than ever.”

“The game doesn’t have to be perfect. The impact lies in the experience—the collaboration, the conversation, the connection.”

THE EPIC-WE PROJECT

EPIC-WE is an acronym for ‘Empowered Participation through Ideating Cultural Worlds and Environments’

A Horizon Europe project focusing on youth imagining, creating and exchanging cultural values and heritage through game-making.

The heart of the project

At its heart, EPIC-WE shows that games are not only entertainment and cultural heritage is not stagnant or dead – when cultural worlds and experiences are brought to life through young people’s imagination, game-making, and cross-sector collaboration both culture and games benefits and become engaging and empowering in new ways.

Game-making as culture-making

EPIC-WE develops, tests, evaluates and delivers a Quadruple Helix Cultural Hub model that brings Higher Education, Cultural Heritage, Creative Industries and Youth (15–25) together as equal partners in culture and games. The model comes to life through Cultural Game Jams - intensive, structured game-making events facilitated by the Cultural Hub partners and where young people co-create and transform heritage, narratives, and values into games through and for culture. Creating and showcasing their games, young people are invited to redefine cultural identity, values, engagement, and experiences and show how games can play a role in co-creating new futures in the intersection of games, heritage, values, and culture.

More than a project

EPIC-WE has not just been a project; it has been a journey empowering young people to shape European culture and futures in games, reframing games as cultural artefacts and game-making as civic participation; it operationalises participatory and co-creative cross-sector collaboration and delivers transferable and open available models, methods, tools, and resources. With the creation of ‘games through culture’ and ‘games for culture,’ games become culture themselves, vehicles for youths’ empowered participation in culture, and carrying the potential to engage new voices and include new identities in shaping European futures in games and culture.

What the project does

The EPIC-WE project is transforming how European culture is created, shared and preserved across Europe and beyond.

1. Unleashing the next generation of culture-makers transforming them from audiences to engaged game-makers.
2. Cultural Game Jams as immersive living laboratories for games and culture using Cultural Game Jam Kits for participatory heritage game creation.
3. Meeting in the middle in QH Cultural Hubs and cross-sector partnerships that break sectoral silos and spark cross-sector collaboration and innovation.
4. Turning culture into playable worlds and experiences that reimagine collections, archives, sites, and artifacts as game-making material.
5. Empowering participation by giving youth the steering wheel in cultural innovation positioning them as fundamental actors in the cultural innovation ecosystem

EPIC-WE shows cross-sector collaboration around game-making as culture-making can generate games and models for engaging heritage; its Quadruple Helix Cultural Hubs and Cultural Game Jams equip young people with cultural-creative competencies, renew institutional practices in games and culture, and – when partners meet each other in the middle to form an epic we - turn culture into a playground where innovation, heritage and imagination empower each other and youth actively transform, co-shape and give voice to the cultural heritage narratives, values and identities we are all part of.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

WHAT IS A CULTURAL GAME JAM?

Cultural Game Jams aim to foster empowered cultural participation, collaboration, and a sense of belonging in culture by engaging young people in game-making as a form of culture-making.

Step inside the Cultural Game Jam: Where games meet culture

Cultural Game Jams (CGJs) empower young people (ages 15–25) as co-creators of culture through game-making processes as a form of culture-making. They blend traditional game jams with cultural imagination and reflection on heritage sites, archives, artifacts, themes, and values. CGJs position games as a key form of culture-making, inviting participants to reimagine, remix, and reconfigure cultural sites, artifacts, and narratives.

The core elements: A Cultural Game Jam Kit for cultural transformation

In EPIC-WE, participants created over 100 Cultural Game Prototypes, all published on the EPIC-WE Resource Site. Using the CGJ framework and CGJ Kit, these prototypes were refined through the project's 12 CGJs. Some of these Games through/for Culture are showcased in the EPIC-WE Games EXPO Catalogue.

The CGJ framework has four phases: Experience, Play, Imagine, Create (EPIC) and focuses on cultural Worlds and Empowerment (WE). CGJ Kit's methods, tools, team roles, EU value cards, and facilitation guides structure the journey. Specialized methods for engaging culture, games, and values, along with transition tools (Ideation Wheel, Expert Council, Playtest, Game Logs),

help teams refine ideas, practice cultural imagination, and integrate feedback as they move toward prototyping and creating their Games through/for Culture.

Through the CGJ framework, participants explore cultural heritage for inspiration, shape ideas through sketches and mock-ups, then prototype and playtest. Each CGJ concludes with the participants showcasing their Games through/for Culture to audiences at an EPIC-WE Games EXPO.

Cultural Game Jams: Transforming audiences into culture-makers and game-makers

CGJs provide deep, multidimensional value across sectors. In culture, they transform audiences into engaged co-creators, strengthening heritage and values and highlighting games as cultural form of expression.

Access the Resource Site
<https://lnk.dk/1326>

In education and youth empowerment, CGJs act as real-world living labs, developing vital skills (collaborative, cultural, creative, technical) and fostering cultural agency, voice, and belonging. The format cultivates an “epic we” – a collective, non-hierarchical space where different participants from different sectors and disciplines collaborate across heritage, culture, and games. In this space, youth express cultural viewpoints and identities and show agency in reimagining culture and games.

The EPIC-WE project results show that Cultural Game Jams hold significant promise at the intersection of cultural heritage and game-making. Key potentials include:

Bridging culture & games: CGJs break down the dichotomy between “culture” and “games,” promoting recognition that games are cultural artifacts in themselves and that cultural game-making fosters meaning, identity, and heritage. This encourages youth to see game-making not merely as entertainment but as part of cultural and societal imagination and participation.

Heritage engagement reinterpreted: Cultural institutions often struggle to engage youth. Cultural Game Jams turn tangible and intangible heritage into game-making material for creative reimagining, rather than static artifacts. Youth remix, narrate, critique, and extend heritage creatively, producing new narratives as Games through/for Culture that connect past, present, and future.

Institutional and industry innovation:

Cultural Game Jams serve as innovation spaces for cultural institutions and creative industries. They act as cross-sector hubs and labs for participatory, co-creative approaches to culture and game-making, enabling organisations to work together and to explore new formats and methods. They also act as experimental sites, supporting talent development, fostering experimentation with value-sensitive, heritage-based game worlds, and opening pathways for culturally and socially engaged game-making. These efforts strengthen institutional and industry innovation, expand educational and industry pipelines, and cultivate a new generation of game-makers shaping culture through games.

Cultural Game Jams are not niche experiments but proven, versatile methods for transforming heritage, education, and creative industries into active, co-creative ecosystems. They reshape relationships from passive consumption to partnership, remaking culture with youth rather than just presenting it. Anyone interested in meaningful participation, future-facing cultural practice, or imaginative learning are invited to adopt Cultural Game Jams. Doing so helps organisations find new ways to interpret the past and cultivate the creative capabilities that will define our cultural futures.

*Rikke Toft Nørgård, EPIC-WE
Coordinator & Lead, Aarhus University*

Level completed!

Achievement unlocked: Games through Culture

...but the journey continues!
Explore the next level with the Games
for Culture EXPO Catalogue
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18461207>